

Lattice Boltzmann Simulation Of MHD Natural Convection In A Nanofluid-Filled Enclosure With Non-Uniform Heating On Both Side Walls

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Abstract : This paper examines the natural convection in a square enclosure filled with a water-Al₂O₃ nanofluid and is subjected to a magnetic field. The side walls of the cavity have spatially varying sinusoidal temperature distributions. The horizontal walls are adiabatic. Lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) is applied to solve the coupled equations of flow and temperature fields. This study has been carried out for the pertinent parameters in the following ranges: Rayleigh number of the base fluid, Ra=103 to 106, Hartmann number varied from Ha=0 to 90, phase deviation ($\gamma=0, \pi/4, \pi/2, 3\pi/4$ and π) and the solid volume fraction of the nanoparticles between = 0 and 6%. The results show that the heat transfer rate increases with an increase of the Rayleigh number but it decreases with an increase of the Hartmann number. For $\gamma=\pi/2$ and Ra=105 the magnetic field augments the effect of nanoparticles. At Ha=0, the greatest effects of nanoparticles are obtained at $\gamma = 0$ and $\pi/4$ for Ra=104 and 105 respectively.

Keywords : Lattice Boltzmann Method, magnetic field, Natural convection, nanofluid, Sinusoidal temperature distribution

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